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Title: Rare earth element geochemistry of sulphide weathering in the São Domingos mine area (Iberian Pyrite Belt): a proxy for fluid-rock interaction and ancient mining pollution

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Abstract: Gossan, disseminated orebody waste, other mining wastes and acid mine drainage (AMD) in the abandoned São Domingos mine area (Iberian Pyrite Belt, IPB, Portugal) have been analyzed for their major ions and rare earth elements (REE). The main aim is to understand REE mobility during sulphide weathering so that the lanthanoid series can be used both as a record of the water-rock interaction and as a tool for identifying impacts of AMD on natural ecosystems. North-American Shale Composite (NASC)-normalized REE patterns corresponding to the disseminated orebody waste are relatively flat ($EMREE = -0.02 \pm 0.11$). However, NASC-normalized REE distributions in AMD from sulphide oxidation tend to be enriched in the middle-REE (MREE) compared to the light-REE (LREE) and heavy-REE (HREE). As a consequence, gossan resulting from supergene alteration of massive sulphide presents an evident NASC-normalized MREE-depleted signature. Thus, the overall water-sulphide interaction defines complementary convex ($EMREE = +0.71 \pm 0.25$) and concave ($EMREE = -0.30 \pm 0.12$) NASC-normalized patterns in draining waters and oxidation products, respectively, which are clearly described for the first time in this study. The percent loss of REE during sulphide supergene oxidation was evaluated using the isocon method, ranging from 0% to -19% for LREE and HREE, and from -22% to -44% for MREE.

The EMREE parameter has been proposed to quantify the curvature in the MREE segment ($EMREE > 0$ for MREE-enriched signatures; < 0 for MREE-depleted signatures; and $= 0$ for horizontal patterns). The mobility degree of REE in São Domingos has been studied by means of most readily mobile fraction resulting from water-minesoil interactions. Solutions extracted from minesoils have NASC-normalized patterns with MREE-enriched signature ($EMREE = +0.68 \pm 0.34$) similar to AMD. Sulphate salts and poorly crystalline iron oxyhydroxysulphates act as a source of labile MREE by dissolution and/or desorption processes and could explain the MREE-enriched signatures in solution. The São Domingos stream, although it has been highly affected by AMD, flows into the Guadiana river that has an estuarine system where pollution is considerably attenuated due to the mixing, according to the metal geoaccumulation indexes currently used in the literature. However, sediments of this estuary were also analyzed and reflect MREE-enriched signatures ($EMREE = +0.25 \pm 0.03$), which demonstrate that this apparently non-polluted estuarine system is being certainly affected by historical mining activities from IPB. The EMREE index is more sensitive to recognize curved MREE signatures than other normalized ratios as (La/Gd)NASC, validating the use of REE patterns as a proxy for environmental pollution by AMD.

Letter to the editor of Chemical Geology.

25.03.2010

Dear Editorial Assistant,

Herewith we submit a manuscript entitled: "Rare earth element geochemistry of sulphide weathering in the São Domingos mine area (Iberian Pyrite Belt): a proxy for fluid-rock interaction and ancient mining pollution". The main aim of the current paper is to understand the REE mobility during sulphide weathering so that lanthanoid series could be used both as a witness for the water-rock interaction and as a tool for identifying impacts of acidic sulphate waters on natural ecosystems. The goals of the study could be of interest to the Chemical Geology readership for the following reasons:

1. This study has potential to contribute to the understanding of the mechanisms controlling lanthanoid mobility in acidic sulphate systems.
2. The paper presents new data for the REE in sulphide-rich volcanic rocks, gossans, acid mine drainages (AMD), mining impacted soils, and mine/industrial waste.
3. These data, in conjunction with analyses of estuarine sediments, are utilized to understand the formation of AMD and to use REE as a measure of AMD pollution in sediment records that may not necessarily possess anomalous base metal concentrations.

None of the results, data, ideas and interpretations has previously been published. All co-authors have collaborated in the manuscript and agree to its submission to Chemical Geology. We are looking forward to hearing from you and hope you will consider our manuscript for publication in your journal.

Yours sincerely,

Rafael Pérez-López.

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Rare earth element geochemistry of sulphide weathering in the São Domingos mine area (Iberian Pyrite Belt): a proxy for fluid-rock interaction and ancient mining pollution.

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17 **ABSTRACT**

18

19 Gossan, disseminated orebody waste, other mining wastes and acid mine drainage (AMD)
20 in the abandoned São Domingos mine area (Iberian Pyrite Belt, IPB, Portugal) have been
21 analyzed for their major ions and rare earth elements (REE). The main aim is to understand
22 REE mobility during sulphide weathering so that the lanthanoid series can be used both as a
23 record of the water-rock interaction and as a tool for identifying impacts of AMD on natural
24 ecosystems. North-American Shale Composite (NASC)-normalized REE patterns
25 corresponding to the disseminated orebody waste are relatively flat ($E_{\text{MREE}} = -0.02 \pm 0.11$).
26 However, NASC-normalized REE distributions in AMD from sulphide oxidation tend to be
27 enriched in the middle-REE (MREE) compared to the light-REE (LREE) and heavy-REE
28 (HREE). As a consequence, gossan resulting from supergene alteration of massive sulphide
29 presents an evident NASC-normalized MREE-depleted signature. Thus, the overall water-
30 sulphide interaction defines complementary convex ($E_{\text{MREE}} = +0.71 \pm 0.25$) and concave
31 ($E_{\text{MREE}} = -0.30 \pm 0.12$) NASC-normalized patterns in draining waters and oxidation products,
32 respectively, which are clearly described for the first time in this study. The percent loss of
33 REE during sulphide supergene oxidation was evaluated using the isocon method, ranging
34 from 0% to -19% for LREE and HREE, and from -22% to -44% for MREE.

35 The E_{MREE} parameter has been proposed to quantify the curvature in the MREE segment
36 ($E_{\text{MREE}} > 0$ for MREE-enriched signatures; < 0 for MREE-depleted signatures; and $= 0$ for
37 horizontal patterns). The mobility degree of REE in São Domingos has been studied by means
38 of most readily mobile fraction resulting from water-minesoil interactions. Solutions extracted
39 from minesoils have NASC-normalized patterns with MREE-enriched signature ($E_{\text{MREE}} =$
40 $+0.68 \pm 0.34$) similar to AMD. Sulphate salts and poorly crystalline iron oxyhydroxysulphates

41 act as a source of labile MREE by dissolution and/or desorption processes and could explain
42 the MREE-enriched signatures in solution. The São Domingos stream, although it has been
43 highly affected by AMD, flows into the Guadiana river that has a estuarine system where
44 pollution is considerably attenuated due to the mixing, according to the metal
45 geoaccumulation indexes currently used in the literature. However, sediments of this estuary
46 were also analyzed and reflect MREE-enriched signatures ($E_{\text{MREE}} = +0.25 \pm 0.03$), which
47 demonstrate that this apparently non-polluted estuarine system is being certainly affected by
48 historical mining activities from IPB. The E_{MREE} index is more sensitive to recognize curved
49 MREE signatures than other normalized ratios as $(\text{La}/\text{Gd})_{\text{NASC}}$, validating the use of REE
50 patterns as a proxy for environmental pollution by AMD.

51

52 **Keywords:** Rare earth elements; Gossan; Acid mine drainage; Mining wastes; Minesoils;
53 Estuary pollution

54

55 **1. INTRODUCTION**

56

57 Gossans (iron oxide-rich caps) are formed when the top of sulphide orebody is oxidized in
58 flowing or standing water resulting in acidic leachates containing high concentrations of
59 sulphate, iron and metals. Pollution caused by such waters, often referred to as acid rock
60 drainage (ARD), results from natural geochemical processes that are common in geological
61 environments where sulphide deposits abound. However, the mining and extractive activity
62 involves the production of considerable wastes that accelerate the natural processes and
63 contribute to the environmental deterioration. The drainage resulting from oxidation of
64 sulphide-rich wastes derived from mining activity by oxygenated water is known as Acid
65 Mine Drainage (AMD). Low temperature geochemical processes including generation of
66 ARD or AMD, collectively called acid drainages, may be recorded by fractionation in the
67 lanthanoid series or rare earth elements (REE). Thus, REE patterns could be used to identify
68 the water-rock interactions that govern the composition of acidic discharges emanating from
69 the sulphide orebody and mining waste (Worrall and Pearson, 2001). Indeed, numerous
70 investigations have reported on the REE geochemistry of acidic sulphate waters (e.g.
71 Johannesson and Lyons, 1995; Elbaz-Poulichet and Dupuy, 1999; Johannesson and Zhou,
72 1999; Verplanck et al., 1999; Gimeno et al., 2000; Gammons et al., 2005; Olías et al., 2005;
73 Ferreira da Silva et al., 2009). All these works describe that these acid draining waters show
74 often shale-normalized patterns enriched in middle-REE (MREE) with respect to light-REE
75 (LREE) and heavy-REE (HREE). Albeit, it is important to consider some exceptions
76 indicating MREE-enrichment is neither showed by all acid-sulphate systems (e.g. Bozau et
77 al., 2008) nor restricted to acidic pH (e.g. Leybourne and Johannesson, 2008). However, the
78 only existing study describing both weathered sulphide and gossan from a Mining Camp

79 (New Brunswick, Canada) observed no significant REE fractionation in the oxidation Fe-rich
80 product (Leybourne et al., 2006). Therefore, the overall REE fractionation from water-
81 sulphide interaction has not been yet fully described.

82 The processes controlling the MREE enrichment observed in acidic waters are not well-
83 understood and it remains unclear whether MREE fractionation is inherited from the lithology
84 of the parent rocks along subsurface flow paths or is a consequence of aqueous processes.
85 Different hypotheses explaining MREE-enriched signatures are: the acid leaching or
86 dissolution of MREE-bearing amorphous iron oxyhydroxides (Johannesson and Zhou, 1999);
87 fractionation by surface/solution reactions between MREE-enriched minerals and acid waters
88 (Sholkovitz, 1995); stabilization and coagulation by colloidal material (Elderfield et al.,
89 1990); and the combined action of different mechanisms. Geochemical processes acting
90 during weathering of sulphide in mining environments and transport in acidic streams to
91 enrich the waters in the MREE, compared to the LREE and HREE, may be studied through the
92 mobility of REE in acid minesoils developed around historic and active mining areas
93 (Fernández-Caliani et al., 2009).

94 The current research is focused on studying REE patterns of sulphide orebody, gossan,
95 mining wastes, acidic waters and soils at the São Domingos mine area (Iberian Pyrite Belt,
96 IPB). The main aims are the following: (1) to describe the overall REE fractionation process
97 during the weathering of sulphide mineralization to form gossan and acid sulphate waters; (2)
98 to study the REE mobility degree in minesoils by means of lab-experiments of water-soil
99 interaction, and thus, explain their influence on the rivers of the region; and (3) to define a
100 parameter that allows the quantification of typical MREE-enriched signatures of acid
101 environments as an evaluation tool for identifying pollution by acid drainages on natural
102 ecosystems. The Guadiana river drains water impacted by abandoned mining activities at São

103 Domingos mine and discharges pollution through its estuary into the Atlantic Ocean. The
104 REE fractionation patterns as a proxy method for determination of mining pollution were
105 preliminarily tested by studying the surface sediments from the estuary of the Guadiana river,
106 with a view to developing a future plan to evaluate anthropogenic impacts in dated
107 environmental records.

108

109

110 2. ENVIRONMENTAL SETTING

111

112 The Guadiana river, one of the most important rivers of the Iberian Peninsula, has a total
113 length of 810 km, of which the last 200 km constitute the border between Portugal and Spain
114 (Fig. 1). The southern part of the Guadiana river is located almost completely in the Central
115 Domain of the South Portuguese Zone (Fig. 1), crossing the materials of IPB, one of the most
116 important metal bearing areas in the world, with around 1700 million tonnes of original
117 reserves of volcanogenic massive sulphide (VMS) deposits (Sáez et al., 1999). Mining
118 activity in the IPB started in the Third Millennium B.C. (Nocete et al., 2005), and was
119 especially intense from the middle of the 19th century (Morral, 1990). The exploitation of the
120 sulphide deposits produced huge amounts of wastes that generate highly pollutant AMD
121 discharges and are responsible of the environmental pollution and water quality degradation
122 of the fluvial courses of the region. Presently, mining activity has almost totally ceased,
123 leaving over a hundred abandoned mine sites. The Tinto and Odiel rivers, two of the main
124 rivers in the IPB, flow into the 'Ría de Huelva' Estuary, where the metal pollution transported
125 by these rivers to the Atlantic Ocean makes this estuarine area one of the most contaminated
126 in the world (e.g., Olías et al., 2006; Nieto et al., 2007; Cánovas et al., 2007; Sarmiento,

127 2008). In contrast, the Guadiana river and its estuary, located approx. 50 km west of the
128 Tinto-Odiel estuarine system, have historically been considered as non-contaminated
129 environments (e.g., Ruiz, 2001; González-Pérez et al., 2008), although this estuary also
130 receives acidic discharge from important mines on the Portuguese (São Domingos mine) and
131 Spanish margins (Herrerías and Tharsis mine) in the lower part of the basin (Delgado et al.,
132 2009).

133 São Domingos is one of the most emblematic Portuguese mining districts. The acid
134 discharge from this mine reaches the Chanza river, main effluent (and source pollution) of the
135 Guadiana river. The mining area includes an open pit mine originally capped by an extensive
136 red gossan formed in situ by weathering of massive sulphide mineralization and classified as a
137 massive sulphide gossan (MSG) according to Boyle (2003). The beginning of mining has
138 been dated back to pre-Roman times, and remained active until 1966 when ceased. During the
139 operation period, mine waste and slurries were discharged directly from the mine into the
140 Guadiana river. Nowadays mine pollution is still important (although with less intensity) due
141 to the continuous leaching of the mine residues that are still spread out near the mine complex
142 (Matos, 2004). The mining wastes in the area are highly heterogeneous, and two main groups
143 can be recognized: (1) mine wastes heaped as dumps, including gossanized coarse blocks,
144 volcanic rocks and shales; and (2) industrial wastes derived from ore processing operations,
145 including Roman and modern slags, roasted pyrite piles, smelting ashes and leaching tank
146 refuses. The precise provenance of each waste can be found in Alvarez-Valero et al. (2008)
147 and Pérez-López et al. (2008).

148 In São Domingos, the preferred method for extracting base metals was cementation, in
149 which low-grade Cu ores were roasted in piles and washed with acidic water to extract the
150 soluble Cu that was later precipitated onto Fe fine-grained scrap. At present, the input

151 material for the roasting process may be recognized in the area and corresponds to sulphide
152 orebody stack-piled in dumps (E12; see Fig. 1). It is envisaged that this sulphide ore may have
153 undergone one or more pre-treatments, for example grinding and mixing with host rocks to
154 improve its permeability. This disseminated sulphide waste is the only vestige of
155 mineralization in the mine since the sulphide orebody is submerged by the pit lake.

156

157

158 **3. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

159

160 A total of 55 samples were collected in São Domingos mining area (Fig. 1): 2 to 7
161 samples of each gossan, disseminated orebody waste and other mining wastes, 11 samples of
162 minesoils developed on waste materials and river banks and 3 samples of water draining the
163 mining area. Moreover, 3 samples of surface sediments were collected with a manual drill in
164 the main channel of the estuary of the Guadiana river, for pollution evaluation purposes.
165 Major minerals present in the samples were identified by X-ray diffraction (XRD), and minor
166 phases were detected and identified by means of scanning electron microscopy equipped with
167 an energy dispersive system for microanalysis (SEM-EDS).

168 Gossan, wastes and estuary sediments (approx. 2 kg each) were grounded, oven-dried at
169 40 °C until complete dryness, homogenized and sieved (< 2 mm) for geochemical analysis.
170 Bulk composition of each sample was analyzed by $\text{LiBO}_2\text{-Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ fusion/dilute nitric
171 digestion followed by solution analysis. Volatile phases were calculated by loss on ignition
172 (LOI), and total carbon and sulphur by Leco. Minesoil samples were collected (0-20 cm
173 depth) in a circle about 60 cm in radius and consisted of a homogeneous sample of five sub-
174 sample points (around 2 kg). After sampling, minesoils were dried at room temperature,

175 disaggregated with a wooden rolling pin, homogenized and sieved through a 2 mm screen.
176 Soil samples (< 2mm fraction) were characterized as follows: pH and conductivity in a water
177 suspension (ratio of 1:2.5 soil/water), single step extraction using the ammonium oxalate
178 method (Schwertmann, 1964) designed to extract poorly crystalline iron oxides, including
179 ferrihydrite, schwertmannite and lepidocrocite (Schwertmann, 1991; Bigham et al., 1994),
180 and the total iron oxide contents (i.e., poorly crystalline and crystalline phases), and bulk
181 composition via analysis of solutions resulting from four-acid digestion (HCl-HF-HNO₃-
182 HClO₄).

183 In order to assess the water-minesoil interaction, leaching of soil samples was performed
184 in centrifuge tubes at room temperature with Millipore MQ water under continuous stirring
185 for a period of 24 h using a ratio 1:10 (solid:liquid), following the method DIN 38414-S4
186 (Official German DIN method, 1984). After the leaching period had elapsed, solutions were
187 separated by centrifugation. One representative sample of gossan was also included in the
188 water-leaching experiments. AMD samples (ca. 2 L) were taken from the course of the main
189 acid stream from São Domingos. Conductivity and pH were measured in situ using field
190 portable instruments. Both soil extract solutions and AMD samples were immediately filtered
191 through syringe 0.45- μ m Teflon filters, acidified to pH < 2 with HNO₃ (2%) suprapur and
192 stored at 4°C for chemical analysis.

193 All analysis of bulk solids, AMD samples and soil extract solutions were carried out by
194 Acme Analytical Laboratories Ltd (Vancouver, Canada), accredited under ISO 9002, through
195 its Italian affiliate (ERS Srl, Napoli). The total analysis of major and trace elements (including
196 the REE) of solutions was analyzed by ICP-AES (inductively coupled plasma - atomic
197 emission spectroscopy) and ICP-MS (inductively coupled plasma-mass spectrometry),
198 respectively. To demonstrate the reproducibility of the results, the analysis sequences

199 consisted of calibration standards, standard solutions analysed as an unknown (quality control
200 solutions), method blanks and certified reference solutions/materials. Further details of
201 analytical procedures, accuracy and quality control can be found on Pérez-López et al. (2008).

202 The REE concentrations were normalized using the North American Shale Composite
203 (NASC) values (Haskin et al., 1968), as a proxy for the average composition of the upper
204 crust. Europium anomalies (Eu/Eu^*) were calculated from the expression
205 $\text{Eu}_{\text{NASC}}/\sqrt{[\text{Sm}_{\text{NASC}}\cdot\text{Gd}_{\text{NASC}}]}$ (Taylor and McLennan, 1985). REE speciation calculations were
206 carried out using data from the AMD samples and soil extract solutions with the software
207 CHEAQS Pro 2008.1 (Verweij, 2007). This code takes stability constants of the REE
208 sulphates complexes from NIST compilation (Martell et al., 2004). The REE chlorides,
209 phosphates and hydroxide complexes were also considered in the modelling, however, their
210 percentages were practically negligible because of extremely low concentrations of ligands.

211

212

213 **4. RESULTS**

214

215 **4.1. REE Concentration in disseminated orebody waste and gossan**

216

217 The disseminated orebody waste shows high quartz (25-40%) and pyrite (15-40%)
218 contents, with minor amounts of secondary minerals (goethite, hematite and jarosite) and rare
219 micas. Galena, sphalerite and arsenopyrite are present as minor phases. The mineralogy of the
220 gossan samples is mainly characterized by quartz (70-85%), hematite (5-10%), goethite (1-
221 5%), jarosite (1-5%), beudantite (1-5%) and minor micas. Disseminated orebody waste and
222 gossan chemistry are clearly dominated by Si, Fe and Al, as expected based on the

223 mineralogical composition (Table 1). The contents of Fe₂O₃ and S vary significantly from one
224 material to the other and allow one to distinguish them. Disseminated sulphide mineralization
225 is relatively richer in S (6.86%) due to presence of sulphide minerals. However, gossan is S-
226 poor (0.63%) and relatively Fe₂O₃-rich (30.51%) due to the lack of pyrite and abundance of
227 goethite and hematite. Most of total Fe content in gossan is bounded to iron oxides, of which
228 only 0.1% of Fe is selectively extracted from poorly crystalline iron oxides.

229 Total REE concentrations (Σ REE), Eu/Eu* values and the normalized (La/Gd)_{NASC} and
230 (La/Yb)_{NASC} ratios are shown in Table 1. Higher REE concentrations are found in
231 disseminated orebody waste samples (average of 170.44 mg kg⁻¹) than in gossan samples
232 (average of 76.74 mg kg⁻¹). LREE concentrations are higher than HREE those for all samples.
233 With respect to average NASC-normalized ratios, (La/Yb)_{NASC} are around unity for both
234 orebody waste and gossan, whereas (La/Gd)_{NASC} are close to 1 only in the orebody waste. For
235 gossan samples, average (La/Gd)_{NASC} is 2.02 showing that LREE are dominant over the
236 MREE (see discussion below). Europium anomalies are lacking both in the orebody waste
237 ([Eu/Eu*] = 0.60 to 1.11, average = 0.90) and gossan ([Eu/Eu*] = 0.96 to 1.07, average =
238 1.01), although in some orebody waste samples are slightly negative.

239

240

241 **4.2. REE Concentration in mining wastes**

242

243 Mine wastes (i.e. gossan coarse blocks, volcanic rocks and shales) are characterized by a
244 high content of quartz (up to 85%), K-feldspar (1-5%), kaolinite (1-5%), muscovite (1-5%)
245 and minor hematite, goethite and jarosite. This mineralogy is repeated in the leaching tank
246 refuses (Álvarez-Valero et al., 2008) where gypsum may also be present as an accessory

247 secondary mineral. Both Roman and modern slags from a base-metal smelting process are
248 characterized by high contents of magnetite (up to 40%), quartz (20-35%) and fayalite (15-
249 25%), and lower percentages of hematite and goethite (10-15%), sulphides (mainly pyrite, 10-
250 15%), glass and trace secondary sulphates (e.g., jarosite). Two immiscible glass types
251 (quenched melt) occur as evidence of the base-metal smelting process: (i) the original melt
252 from the mixing of the processing material doped with a flux; and (ii) the metallic alloy
253 segregated from the original melt (Álvarez-Valero et al., 2009). Smelting ashes are composed
254 of quartz (60%), gypsum (20%), K-feldspar (15%) and minor proportions of pyrite (1-5%).
255 Roasted pyrite piles are typically composed by hematite (95%) and minor content of goethite
256 (5%).

257 Major element concentrations for mine and industrial wastes are listed in Tables 2 and 3,
258 respectively. The capacity of these wastes as a source of mobile heavy metals in three
259 environmental scenarios (water leaching, exposition to oxidation and reducing condition) to
260 the mine catchment basin is reported in Pérez-López et al. (2008). In general, Σ REE
261 concentration for mine wastes (ranging from 125.82 to 162.99 mg kg⁻¹; Table 2) is equal to or
262 greater than that for industrial wastes (ranging from 12.24 to 134.85 mg kg⁻¹; Table 3). Note
263 the low Σ REE concentrations for roasted pyrite (average of 12.24 mg kg⁻¹) and modern slags
264 (average of 33.58 mg kg⁻¹) (Table 3). Except gossan coarse blocks and host volcanic rocks +
265 shales, remaining wastes show $(La/Yb)_{NASC} > 1$, indicating an enrichment in LREE with
266 respect to HREE. $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ ratio > 1 also suggests a moderate enrichment in LREE
267 relative to MREE. Average $[Eu/Eu^*]$ values show insignificant Europium anomalies for all
268 samples.

269

270

271 **4.3. REE Concentration in soils**

272

273 The major minerals in acid minesoils are kaolinite and illite (40-60%), quartz (20-30%),
274 jarosite (5-20%), feldspars (5-10%) and gypsum (5-10%). In São Domingos soils, metal
275 sulphate efflorescent salts (e.g., melanterite, rozenite, szomolnokite) and poorly crystalline
276 iron oxides occurring as oxyhydroxides/oxyhydroxysulphates (e.g., schwertmannite)
277 precipitate as aggregates and coatings on the surface of particle grains, and were identified by
278 Fourier-Transform Infrared spectroscopy and SEM (Durães et al., 2008; Pérez-López et al.,
279 2008). The total iron content ranges from 0.92 to 19.53% (average of 12.27% Fe₂O₃; Table 4).
280 The average Fe content bounded to iron oxide is 46±15% relative to the total Fe content, with
281 significant amounts of Fe associated with poorly crystalline iron oxides, i.e. 19±31% with
282 respect to total iron oxides. The concentrations of REE in minesoils are reported in Table 4.
283 ΣREE varies between 50 and 165 mg kg⁻¹ with a median value of 98 mg kg⁻¹. NASC-
284 normalized ratios suggest an enrichment of LREE with respect to MREE and HREE, as
285 indicated by average values of (La/Gd)_{NASC} = 1.39 and (La/Yb)_{NASC} = 1.37. The Eu/Eu*
286 values range from 0.83 to 1.23 (average of 0.98) indicating the lack of significant Eu
287 anomalies.

288

289

290 **4.4. REE Concentration in extract solutions and AMD**

291

292 The leaching experiments reveal that minesoils are capable of producing solutions with
293 low pH values (average of 3.12), high conductivity values (average of 1.1 mS/cm⁻¹) and high
294 sulphate concentrations as the dominant anion (average of 1520 mg L⁻¹) when interacting with

295 water (Table 5). This is so because the most of sulphate efflorescent salts contained in these
296 soils are highly water-soluble and provide an immediate source of acidic sulphate solutions
297 upon dissolution and hydrolysis (Alpers et al., 1994). It is important to note that water-soluble
298 fraction does not include the poorly crystalline iron oxyhydroxysulphate fraction because
299 these phases (e.g., schwertmannite) are water-insoluble (Bigham et al., 1996). On the
300 contrary, solution from gossan-water interaction found to have lower acidity (pH 4.31),
301 conductivity ($115 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) and sulphate concentrations (29.9 mg L^{-1}) than the remaining
302 interactions with minesoils (Table 5). These data are indicative of that gossan, in addition to
303 negligible amounts of poorly crystalline iron oxides, also presents insignificant contents of
304 water-soluble efflorescent salts. Extract solutions exhibit a broad range of ΣREE
305 concentrations from 9.79 to $543.55 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (Table 5). A strong positive linear correlation exists
306 between sulphate and the REE concentrations as an indicative of that dissolution of
307 efflorescent salts also release lanthanides in solution. Samples present high and variable
308 $(\text{La}/\text{Yb})_{\text{NASC}}$ ratios (0.52-2.91) and lower $(\text{La}/\text{Gd})_{\text{NASC}}$ ratios (average of 0.47) suggesting that
309 all these solutions show enrichment of MREE relative to LREE.

310 AMD from São Domingos mine reflect similar hydrogeochemical characteristics to water
311 draining the acidic sulphate soils, as expected (Table 5). Mine water samples are even more
312 acidic than solutions extracted from minesoils (pH around 2.3), which matches a higher
313 conductivity (average of $3.4 \text{ mS}/\text{cm}^{-1}$), sulphate concentration (average of 1890 mg L^{-1}) and
314 ΣREE concentrations (average of $218.07 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$). Again, $(\text{La}/\text{Gd})_{\text{NASC}}$ ratio < 1 for AMD
315 samples means an enrichment of MREE respect to LREE.

316

317

318 **4.5. REE Concentration in estuary sediments of Guadiana river**

319

320 The results of major and rare earth elements for the estuary sediments of Guadiana river
321 are given in Table 6. Σ REE mean concentration is 212.04 mg kg⁻¹. Average NASC-
322 normalized ratios indicate that there are no apparently enrichment of LREE respect to MREE
323 ((La/Gd)_{NASC} ≈ 1), and it is only observed an slightly enrichment of LREE respect to HREE
324 ((La/Yb)_{NASC} = 1.25). Europium anomalies are also lacking in sediments ([Eu/Eu*] = 1.02 to
325 1.07, average = 1.04).

326

327

328 **5. DISCUSSION**

329

330 **5.1. Fractionation during gossan formation and AMD production**

331

332 When normalized against NASC, the disseminated orebody waste displays generally
333 horizontal REE patterns, with all REE around NASC values (Fig. 2a). This REE distribution
334 is not only a consequence of the presence of diluent host rocks (mainly shales) but also the
335 sulphide orebody from the São Domingos mine, whose NASC-normalized REE patterns must
336 be also flat or, at most, slightly increased in MREE like in other VMS deposits from the IBP
337 (Ruiz et al., 2002; Ferreira da Silva, 2009). However, gossan has lower concentrations than
338 sulphide and concave NASC-normalized REE patterns, i.e., tend to be clearly depleted in
339 MREE compared to LREE and HREE (Fig. 2b). Hence, gossan patterns are strongly
340 fractionated compared to massive sulphide mineralization, although they preserve the lack of
341 europium anomalies. Knowing the range of concentrations in the orebody before and after
342 alteration, one can calculate the percent loss or gain of REE during sulphide supergene

343 alteration to form gossan using the isocon method (Grant, 2005) and the Geoiso software
344 (Coehlo, 2006). The isocon is a line that defines those elements which have not suffered any
345 mass change during the process. The gossan would be enriched or depleted with respect to the
346 original sulphide if elements plot above or below the isocon line, respectively. In this case, the
347 element concentrations in the orebody are not exactly known due to the dilution effect
348 existing in the disseminated orebody waste. Even so, the isocon line for REE could be
349 calculated since concentrations in the gossan are certainly known and it has been long
350 reported that HREE are typically immobile during alteration associated with VMS (e.g.
351 Belkabir et al., 2008; and references therein), as also happens elsewhere in the IPB (Dawson
352 et al., 2001; Rosa et al., 2004). Thus, and considering Lu as the immobile element, the
353 percentage M of loss or gain of each remaining REE is estimated as follows:
354 $M = [(1/S) - 1] \times 100$, where S is the immobile isocon defined as the slope of the line of the
355 immobile elements in the isocon diagrams (Fig. 3a).

356 For the São Domingos deposit, the percent loss of REE during supergene weathering is
357 not uniform and ranges from 0 to -44% (Fig. 3b). The relative losses are higher for MREE
358 (average of -34%) than those for LREE and HREE (average of -9%). The immobility of La
359 during weathering of massive sulfides has also been documented in the literature (Belkabir et
360 al., 2008). The existence of jarosite-rich gossans capping the orebody indicates that acid
361 weathering of outcropping sulfide ores could have produced natural ARD prior to any mining
362 activity (Lottermoser, 2003). One could assume that the current AMD waters are equivalent
363 to waters that existed at the time of weathering of massive sulphide and gossan formation
364 sometime in the past, well before any mining occurred. If the gossan is depleted in MREE, it
365 stands to reason that the complementary resulting product, i.e. acid drainages, should exhibit
366 an opposite behaviour in REE elements. Indeed, AMD samples show convex NASC-

367 normalized REE patterns with an evident MREE-enriched signature with respect to LREE and
368 HREE (Fig. 4).

369 The observed upward concave (V-type) and convex (Λ -type) MREE patterns resemble
370 upward concave (W-type) and convex (M-type) lanthanide tetrad effect, respectively
371 (Kawabe, 1992; McLennan, 1994). The tetrad effect plausibly results from the strong fluid-
372 rock interaction in highly evolved silicate magmas (Masuda et al., 1987). This effect is
373 visually represented in chondrite-normalized REE patterns as four successive curved
374 segments (first tetrad: La to Nd; second tetrad: (Pm) to Gd; third tetrad: Gd to Ho; fourth
375 tetrad: Er to Lu), which can be either W- or M-shaped. The quantification of the size of the
376 tetrad effect is often carried out using the method proposed by Monecke et al. (2002).
377 Following the same idea, our own V- and Λ -type effect observed here just for MREE would
378 represent a new index of physico-chemical conditions of fluid-rock weathering prevalent in
379 sulphide mining districts. So far, MREE enrichment has been quantified according to NASC-
380 normalized $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$ and $(Gd/Yb)_{NASC}$ ratios. However, using a single rare earth as
381 representative of a set could hamper the interpretation of REE patterns in case of exclusive
382 fractionation affecting only to such rare earth. Therefore, it would be crucial to assess the
383 significance of the curvature effect in the MREE whole segment. For this reason, we propose
384 the index E_{MREE} to quantify this effect as the normalized difference between the point of
385 maximum curvature of the polynomial curve fitting of the MREE region and its theoretical Y-
386 axis position in case of not enrichment or depletion. The quality of the fit, and hence the
387 significance of the curve formed by data points, was quantify by the squared correlation
388 coefficient, R^2 . The value of E_{MREE} is positive for convex MREE-signatures, negative for
389 concave MREE-signatures and around zero for flat patterns.

390 In the São Domingos mining district, the weathering of the sulphide is the main source of
391 aqueous REE (and pollutants) to catchment basin of acidic waters. The value of E_{MREE} for the
392 disseminated orebody waste is -0.02 ± 0.11 (average of $R^2 = 0.44$). However, the São
393 Domingos gossan is characterized by a value of E_{MREE} of -0.30 ± 0.12 (average of $R^2 = 0.90$),
394 versus $+0.71 \pm 0.25$ (average of $R^2 = 0.93$) of AMD. Previous studies have demonstrated that
395 acid mine waters present NASC-normalized patterns with MREE-enriched signatures
396 (Johannesson and Lyons, 1995; Johannesson and Zhou, 1999). However, we report for first
397 time complementary MREE-depleted signatures in gossan. Apparently, there seems to be
398 contradiction with respect to some works described in the literature indicating that in these
399 acid systems, poorly crystalline iron oxyhydroxysulphates act as a preferential sink of MREE
400 by co-precipitation and adsorption processes (Bau, 1999; Johannesson and Zhou, 1999).
401 Albeit, in our opinion, no such contradiction exists since the amount of these poorly
402 crystalline iron oxyhydroxysulphates in the gossan, extracted using the oxalate method, is
403 very low with respect to crystalline iron oxides (ca. 0.1%). The soluble sulphate aggregates
404 and surface coatings on particles are also minor, and however, their dissolution during the
405 gossan-water interaction experiments produces solutions whose REE patterns are enriched in
406 MREE with respect to LREE and HREE, with a value of E_{MREE} of $+1.33$ ($R^2 = 0.87$; Fig. 4)
407 totally opposed to the bulk composition ($E_{\text{MREE}} = -0.30$). The weathering conditions readily
408 contribute to raise REE in solution through dissolution and desorption from these Fe
409 oxyhydroxysulphate coats (García et al., 2007), this process being the main responsible for
410 MREE enrichments in acid drainages.

411 Gossanization process began with oxidation of sulphide minerals, production of acidic
412 waters and precipitation of poorly crystalline iron oxyhydroxysulphates. In this early stage, it
413 is probable to expect that poorly crystalline Fe-rich residue had MREE-enriched signatures,

414 similar to the acid drainages, due to the preferential retention in these phases. However, as
415 gossanization matures with time, dissolution and re-crystallization of poorly crystalline ferric
416 phases to more crystalline and less soluble minerals (e.g., goethite and hematite), along with
417 the MREE desorption, results in a progressive depletion of MREE. At present, although
418 MREE-enriched sulphate salts and poorly crystalline phases exist in gossan and act as source
419 of MREE in acid drainages, this fraction is minor since do not control the bulk-rock REE
420 concentrations, which show marked MREE-depleted signatures as stated before.

421 The remaining of surrounding rocks do not contain sulphides or are only in minor
422 proportions, however, the circulation of AMD through them can also favour the precipitation
423 of these soluble salts and poorly crystalline iron phases. Albeit, MREE-bearing fraction is
424 also presented in negligible proportions since bulk-rock REE concentrations have not convex
425 NASC-profiles. Gossanized coarse blocks, volcanic rocks and shales have REE
426 concentrations close to NASC values distributed in relatively flat normalized patterns, or
427 slightly enriched in HREE (Fig. 5a). With respect to industrial wastes, NASC profiles are also
428 flat or slightly enriched in HREE, although with concentrations of approx. 12, 5, 1.6, 1.4, 1.3
429 times lower than those of NASC for roasted pyrite piles, modern slags, Roman slags, smelting
430 ashes and leaching tanks, respectively (Fig. 5b). Thus, industrial wastes must contribute to a
431 lesser extent to aqueous REE in AMD.

432

433

434 **5.2. Mobility and speciation in the acidic soil environment**

435

436 Acid sulphate soils are a highly favourable environment for mobilisation of lanthanoids
437 and represent the main reservoir of readily leachable REE for fluvial courses (Åstrom et al.,

2009). NASC-normalised REE distributions for the total minesoils show flat to slightly MREE and HREE-depleted profiles (Fig. 6a). However, the water-soluble fraction, which chiefly reflects the more mobile fraction composed of typical sulphate efflorescence salts within soils, are enriched in MREE and depleted in LREE and HREE (Fig. 6b). Convex (Λ -type) MREE-signatures for soil extracts reach a value of E_{MREE} of $+0.68 \pm 0.34$ (average of $R^2 = 0.77$) and are consistent with the typical REE fractionation patterns reported for AMD. Therefore, comparison of the REE patterns for the bulk composition and those for the extract solutions reveals that soluble sulphate aggregates and surface coatings in soils, although in higher proportions than gossan, are not abundant enough to control the bulk lanthanide concentration and fractionation model. Even so, this minor fraction is an important source of labile MREE by dissolution and plays the main role in MREE-enriched patterns for AMD. Moreover, just considering the soil samples collected on the banks of the local acidic stream, i.e. S1, S4, S5, S8, S10 and S11, one can observe a relatively good positive correlation between the proportions of Fe associated with poorly crystalline Fe oxyhydroxysulphates with respect to the total iron oxide content and the convexity index (E_{MREE}) obtained in the NASC-normalised REE distribution diagrams of the soil extracts ($R^2 = 0.82$). This also reflects the importance of the desorption process from water-insoluble oxyhydroxysulphates in the buffering of this MREE source in stream soils and MREE-enriched signatures for AMD. Our results are similar to those reported for stream waters and associated soils/sediments in Bathurst mining camp (New Brunswick, Canada) and Tharsis mining area (Iberian Pyrite Belt) by Leybourne and Johannesson (2008) and Fernández-Caliani et al. (2009), respectively. We cannot ignore that MREE-enriched organic colloids are also able to contribute to the MREE enrichments of the São Domingos stream waters (e.g., Elderfield et al., 1990; Sholkovitz, 1995).

462 In IPB mining districts, although applicable to any other acid sulphate environments,
463 readily dissolution of REE-bearing Fe oxyhydroxysulphates salts, along with oxidation of
464 sulphide particles incorporated into the soil by wind action, cause the release of acidity and
465 high sulphate and metal concentrations, as observed in the leaching experiments. Consistent
466 with numerous previous studies (e.g., Johannesson and Lyons, 1995; Elbaz-Poulichet and
467 Dupuy, 1999; Gimeno et al., 2000; Olías et al., 2005; Zhao et al., 2007; Fernández-Caliani et
468 al., 2009), sulphate is the main ligand in solutions extracted from soil and AMD from São
469 Domingos and controls the REE speciation model. REE-sulphate complexes, mainly
470 monosulphato-complexes (LnSO_4^+), are the primary aqueous form for most of soil extracts
471 and AMD (60-90%), whereas free ionic species (Ln^{3+} , 10-40%) are the next most abundant
472 dissolved REE form (Fig. 7a). In AMD and extract solutions from S5 and S7 soils where
473 dissolved sulphate concentrations are the highest ($> 2000 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$), the proportion of $\text{Ln}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$
474 species in solution was also found to be important, reaching up to 10% with respect to total
475 REE species (Fig. 7b,c). Only when dissolved sulphate concentrations are low ($< 240 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$),
476 REE speciation becomes clearly dominated for over 50% by Ln^{3+} species, as occur in
477 solutions extracted from gossan, and S3 and S9 minesoils (Fig. 7d).

478 Stability constants for REE-sulphate complexes are relatively uniform across the
479 lanthanide series, which is expected in view of the great chemical similarity of neighbouring
480 REE (Millero, 1992; Schijf and Byrne, 2004). It is noted however a small increase in stability
481 constants of MREE-sulphate complexes with respect to LREE, and mainly in relation to
482 HREE (see Fig. 4 in Schijf and Byrne, 2004). This explains that in São Domingos mine the
483 average ratio of MREE sulphate complexes (LnSO_4^+ and $\text{Ln}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$; 62.85%) for soil extracts
484 and AMD is slightly higher than that of LREE sulphate complexes (62.76%) and HREE
485 sulphate complexes (59.56%) (Fig. 7b-d). Some authors use the slightly higher partitioning of

486 dissolved MREE into sulphate complexes as a secondary explanation for convex (Λ -type)
487 signatures in acid sulphate waters (e.g., Zhao et al., 2007). However, we feel that these
488 variations are insignificant and can be within the uncertainty of data, and thus, the aqueous
489 sulphate complexation is not expected to fractionate the REE in acidic waters/soils, as also
490 pointed out by other investigations (e.g., Johannesson and Lyons, 1995; Johannesson and
491 Zhou, 1999; Leybourne et al., 2006; Fernández-Caliani et al., 2009). Hence, the release of
492 MREE from dissolution and/or desorption processes in soluble salts and poorly crystalline
493 iron oxyhydroxysulphates seem to be the main explanation to account for the MREE
494 fractionation observed in the acidic waters.

495

496

497 **5.3. REE signatures as an indicator of AMD pollution**

498

499 IPB hosts more than 80 massive sulphide deposits exploited and around 2×10^8 m³ of
500 waste material (Sáez et al., 1999). As stated before, the acid leachates, rich in metals, derived
501 from the superficial oxidation of sulphides contained in these wastes are mainly drained by
502 the Tinto and Odiel rivers, which discharge a high load of acidity, sulphate and metals into the
503 Huelva Estuary (e.g., Olías et al., 2006; Nieto et al., 2007; Cánovas et al., 2007; Sarmiento,
504 2008). Tinto and Odiel river waters also contain high concentrations of aqueous REE, mainly
505 as soluble sulphate complexes, in comparison with those of the river freshwaters worldwide
506 average, and show NASC-normalized patterns dominated by distinctive MREE enrichments
507 of acidic sulphate environments (Fig. 8; Elbaz-Poulichet and Dupuy, 1999). According to our
508 results and those reported by Fernández-Caliani et al. (2009), it is realistic to affirm that REE
509 patterns of IPB fluvial courses reflect the REE signature of acid streams, and hence water-soil

510 interactions, from mine catchment basins. Given the acidity of these fluvial courses (pH < 4),
511 REE patterns are maintained throughout their pathway without further fractionation to reach
512 the estuary.

513 In the Tinto-Odiel estuarine system, acidity decreases and salinity increases as seawater
514 mixes with riverwater, producing metal removal processes that result in the metallic
515 enrichment of sediments (Achterberg et al., 2003; Braungardt et al., 2003; López-González et
516 al., 2006). González-Pérez et al. (2008) estimated that the average concentrations of surface
517 sediments reach approx. 1574, 1051, 523, 278, 66 and 30 mg kg⁻¹ of Zn, Cu, Pb, As, Cr and
518 Ni, respectively. Estuarine reactions also modify the relative abundance of dissolved REE
519 reaching the oceans. In estuaries only affected by saline mixing processes, the removal order
520 is as follows $LREE \geq MREE > HREE$, and thus, NASC-normalized REE patterns observed in
521 estuarine sediments show a LREE enrichment relative to MREE and HREE (Sholkovitz and
522 Szymczak, 2000; Lawrence and Kamber, 2006). In the Tinto-Odiel estuary, saline and acid
523 mixing processes prevents particles to adsorb REE, and thus, REE concentration in sediments
524 are lower than those observed in sediments from rivers and estuaries not affected by AMD
525 (Elbaz-Poulichet and Dupuy, 1999). Nevertheless, the preferential scavenging of Fe
526 oxyhydroxides over MREE favours that sediments preserve NASC-normalized patterns with
527 convex MREE-signatures typical of environments affected by acidic sulphate contributions
528 (Fig. 8; Borrego et al., 2005).

529 In the Tinto-Odiel estuary, the high metal concentrations in sediments through various
530 geochemical parameters such as geoaccumulation index defined by Müller (1981) allow the
531 classification of this estuary as a highly polluted environmental system (Ruiz, 2001;
532 González-Pérez et al., 2008). Mining pollution can even be dated from vertical sedimentary
533 records using metal concentration (López-González et al., 2006) and REE fractionation

534 (Borrego et al., 2005). However, the use of REE fractionation to identify contamination by
535 AMD in this system a priori does not seem to be too useful a tool since this information can
536 be obtained more easily from metal concentrations in sediments.

537 In this paper, we propose the use of REE patterns as a proxy for environmental systems
538 slightly affected by AMD pollution. Acid stream waters from São Domingos flow into the
539 Guadiana river and an estuary that empties into the Atlantic Ocean. In the Guadiana river, the
540 lower influence of mine effluents over the total water flow and the existence of some
541 reservoirs attenuating the metal concentration favour that fluvial and estuarine sediments
542 present a less significant contamination, with average values of 150, 50, 39 and 27 mg kg⁻¹ of
543 Zn, Cr, As and Cu = Pb = Ni, respectively, for surface samples (González-Pérez et al., 2008).
544 Based on Müller's geoaccumulation index, this estuary can be considered as a non AMD-
545 polluted environmental system (González-Pérez et al., 2008). In fact, some authors attribute
546 the existent contamination to some areas of agricultural production (Ruiz, 2001). On the
547 contrary, NASC-normalized REE distributions for estuary sediments of Guadiana river
548 obtained in this work show clearly MREE-enriched profiles (Fig. 9). Convex (Λ -type)
549 MREE-signatures reach a value of E_{MREE} of $+0.25 \pm 0.03$ and agree with the REE
550 fractionation reported for AMD and water-minesoil interactions. Given that NASC-
551 normalized ratios (e.g. $(\text{La}/\text{Gd})_{\text{NASC}} \approx 1$; see results section) showed no MREE fractionation
552 in the estuary sediments, and however, the curvature of these segments can be readily
553 recognized in the patterns (the curve fitting of the MREE segment has an average value of R^2
554 = 0.94), we recommend the use of E_{MREE} index instead of these ratios as a tool to asses the
555 REE behaviour during fluid-rock weathering on sulphide mining districts. Definitively, these
556 results of REE fractionation demonstrate that this apparently non-polluted estuarine system is
557 being certainly affected by abandoned mining activities from IPB. Based on these data, there

558 is an ongoing project to assess spatio-temporal AMD-pollution in both surface and vertical
559 sediment records from the degree of MREE enrichment (E_{MREE}).

560 Gossan represents a natural acid drainage environment that serves as an analogue to the
561 conditions under which sulphate and Fe-oxide possibly formed on the planet Mars. Indeed,
562 the Rio Tinto basin is recognized as a terrestrial analogue model for life habitats on Mars
563 since the alteration mechanisms may be similar to subsurface weathering of the Martian crust
564 (Fernández-Remolar et al., 2008). Hence, owing to the sensibility of REE patterns to detect
565 sulphide oxidation processes, we suggest MREE signatures be utilized as an indicator of
566 aqueous weathering on the acidic sulphate rocks found in Mars.

567

568

569 **6. CONCLUSIONS**

570

571 According to a study carried out in São Domingos mine, lanthanoid series or rare earth
572 elements (REE) could be an effective proxy for environmental pollution by acid mine
573 drainage (AMD) in Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB). The REE fractionation during sulphide and
574 mine wastes weathering is a witness for identifying impacts of AMD on natural ecosystems as
575 derived from the following conclusions:

- 576 1. NASC-normalized patterns corresponding to a disseminated orebody waste show a
577 horizontal distribution in REE ($E_{\text{MREE}} = -0.02 \pm 0.11$). However, the overall water-
578 sulphide interaction defines complementary convex and concave MREE-signatures in
579 AMD ($E_{\text{MREE}} = +0.71 \pm 0.25$) and gossan ($E_{\text{MREE}} = -0.30 \pm 0.12$), respectively.

- 580 2. The E_{MREE} parameter is a novel index that gives an idea of the curvature degree in the
581 MREE segment. The size of this index was quantified as the normalized difference
582 between the point of maximum curvature of the polynomial curve fitting of the MREE
583 region and its theoretical Y-axis position in case of not enrichment or depletion. The
584 value of E_{MREE} is positive for convex MREE-signatures, negative for concave MREE-
585 signatures and around zero for flat patterns.
- 586 3. Unlike the bulk composition, solutions from gossan-water interaction have NASC-
587 normalized patterns with MREE-enriched signature ($E_{\text{MREE}} = +1.33$) similar to AMD.
- 588 4. NASC-normalized REE patterns of minesoils are flat to slightly MREE and HREE-
589 depleted profiles. However, extracts from minesoils also have MREE-enriched
590 signatures ($E_{\text{MREE}} = +0.68 \pm 0.34$).
- 591 5. Sulphate efflorescent salts and poorly crystalline iron oxyhydroxysulphates are
592 suggested as a source of labile MREE by dissolution and/or desorption processes,
593 explaining the MREE-enriched signatures in solution. The acid sulphate waters from
594 minesoil-water interactions mobilize the REE predominantly as sulphate complexes
595 (mainly LnSO_4^+). The REE mobility and behaviour in the IPB mining catchments
596 transfers its geochemical signature to strongly AMD-polluted rivers and estuaries of the
597 region (Tinto-Odiel system).
- 598 6. However, the São Domingos acid stream through Guadiana river flows into an
599 apparently non-polluted estuarine system, where metal pollution is considerably diluted
600 and attenuated. Nevertheless, sediments of this estuary were also analyzed and reflect
601 MREE-enriched signatures ($E_{\text{MREE}} = +0.25 \pm 0.03$).
- 602 7. The convexity index (E_{MREE}) assesses the significance of the curvature effect in the
603 MREE whole segment, thus being a more sensitive tool to recognize concave and

604 convex MREE signatures than other NASC-normalized ratios where a single element
605 represents to a set such as $(La/Gd)_{NASC}$. Hence, REE fractionation through this
606 parameter can serve as a good proxy for AMD-pollution in sulphide-rich mining
607 environments.

608

609

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611

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615

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802

803 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

804

805 FIGURE 1. Sampling location map of the São Domingos mining district: (i) Mining wastes ⇒
806 E1 - Modern slag, E2 - Roman slag, E3 - Smelting ashes, E4 - Gossan coarse blocks, E5 -
807 Gossan, E7 - Gossanized volcanic rocks, E8 - Host volcanic rocks + shales, E9 - Shales,
808 E11 - Roasted pyrite, E12 - Pyrite orebody, A1 - Leaching tanks; (ii) Minesoils (S) ⇒ F -
809 Leached materials in seasonal flooded areas, L - Mine landfill, UL - Urban contaminated
810 landfills, AW - Unvegetated area affected by extreme acid waters; (iii) Acid mine
811 drainage (AMD); and (iv) Estuary sediments of Guadiana river (GE).

812 FIGURE 2. NASC-normalized REE patterns for (a) disseminated orebody waste and (b)
813 gossan. The shadowed area refers to the variability range and dash line to mean value.

814 FIGURE 3. (a) Isocon diagram of REE concentration in the orebody sulphide (Co) vs.
815 concentration in the gossan (Cf); and (b) Percent element loss plot showing relative loss
816 of the REE in average gossan compared to average orebody sulphide. Note the relatively
817 highest loss of middle-REE in the gossan. See text for calculations. In (a) CV: line of
818 constant volume and CM: line of constant mass.

819 FIGURE 4. NASC-normalized REE patterns for acid mine drainage (AMD) and aqueous
820 solution extracted from gossan sample. The shadowed area refers to the variability range
821 and dash line to mean value for AMD.

822 FIGURE 5. NASC-normalized REE patterns for (a) mine wastes and (b) industrial wastes.
823 Each pattern represents the mean value of samples collected.

824 FIGURE 6. NASC-normalized REE patterns for (a) bulk minesoils and (b) aqueous solutions
825 extracted from minesoils (S).

826 FIGURE 7. Results of aqueous REE speciation: (a) average ratios of REE species for average
827 AMD and extract solutions; (b), (c) and (d) full REE speciation of some representative
828 samples: average AMD, solution extracted from minesoil S5 and solution extracted from
829 gossan sample, respectively. Ln refers to any REE from La to Lu.

830 FIGURE 8. Comparative diagram showing NASC-normalized REE patterns for São
831 Domingos acid stream, estuary sediments of the Guadiana river (see also Fig. 9), acid
832 waters of the Odiel and Tinto rivers (Elbaz-Poulichet and Dupuy, 1999), and estuary
833 sediments of the Tinto river (Borrego et al., 2005).

834 FIGURE 9. NASC-normalized REE patterns for estuary sediments of the Guadiana river.

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837 TABLES CAPTIONS

838

839 TABLE 1. Major elements and REE concentrations in both disseminated orebody waste and
840 gossan samples.

841 TABLE 2. Major elements and REE concentrations in mine waste samples.

842 TABLE 3. Major elements and REE concentrations in industrial waste samples.

843 TABLE 4. Major elements and REE concentrations in minesoil samples.

844 TABLE 5. Values of pH and electrical conductivity (EC), major anions and REE
845 concentrations in aqueous solutions extracted from minesoils (S) and gossan, and acid
846 mine drainage samples (AMD).

847 TABLE 6. Major elements and REE concentrations in estuary sediment samples of the
848 Guadiana river.

Figure 1

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 2

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Figure 9

Samples	Disseminated orebody waste					Gossan		
	E12-1	E12-2	E12-3	E12-4	E12-5	E5-1	E5-2	E5-3
Major elements (%)								
SiO ₂	54.54	72.25	35.52	36.15	40.87	55.97	nm	58.98
Al ₂ O ₃	9.71	7.16	11.18	14.16	11.61	2.33	2.65	4.42
Fe ₂ O ₃	13.81	8.55	21.88	13.32	18.75	32.40	35.19	23.94
MgO	0.45	0.06	0.11	0.17	0.13	0.01	0.03	0.19
CaO	0.07	0.19	0.31	0.34	1.05	0.01	0.03	0.50
Na ₂ O	1.20	0.58	0.48	1.09	0.98	0.04	0.05	0.23
K ₂ O	2.03	1.02	1.50	2.68	2.01	0.24	0.25	0.71
TiO ₂	0.53	0.40	0.42	0.99	0.82	0.47	1.37	1.45
P ₂ O ₅	0.08	0.13	0.17	0.17	0.11	0.08	0.10	0.10
MnO	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.003	0.03
LOI	16.90	8.90	27.20	29.50	22.60	5.40	nm	7.10
S	2.96	3.13	11.46	7.32	9.45	0.60	0.43	0.86
Total	99.33	99.26	98.78	98.58	98.94	96.96	-	97.65
Rare earth elements (mg kg⁻¹)								
La	24.10	27.20	63.00	34.00	25.90	15.60	13.10	23.10
Ce	47.30	53.00	128.90	66.20	49.40	27.30	26.49	42.90
Pr	5.35	6.17	14.65	7.75	5.82	3.11	2.90	5.10
Nd	20.40	23.10	56.10	30.60	23.40	10.70	10.80	17.30
Sm	4.20	5.00	11.00	5.90	4.60	1.60	1.70	2.90
Eu	0.74	1.00	1.34	1.24	1.05	0.29	0.30	0.58
Gd	3.91	4.46	9.26	4.69	3.99	0.95	1.10	2.57
Tb	0.76	0.85	1.69	0.81	0.64	0.17	0.20	0.50
Dy	5.14	4.75	9.46	4.45	3.73	1.19	1.50	3.42
Ho	1.17	0.98	1.92	0.88	0.77	0.29	0.40	0.70
Er	3.70	2.97	6.02	2.56	2.24	1.00	1.10	2.52
Tm	0.56	0.47	0.88	0.37	0.36	0.14	0.20	0.39
Yb	3.90	2.81	5.50	2.47	2.18	1.22	1.60	2.52
Lu	0.59	0.39	0.77	0.40	0.33	0.18	0.20	0.40
ΣREE	121.82	133.15	310.49	162.32	124.41	63.74	61.59	104.90
Eu/Eu*	0.83	0.96	0.60	1.07	1.11	1.07	1.00	0.96
La/Gd _{NASC}	1.00	0.99	1.11	1.18	1.05	2.67	1.94	1.46
La/Yb _{NASC}	0.60	0.94	1.11	1.33	1.15	1.24	0.79	0.89

nm: not measured

Table 1

Samples	Gossan coarse blocks							Gossanized volcanics			Host volcanic rocks + shales			Shales			
	E4-1	E4-2	E4-3	E4-4	E4-5	E4-6	E4-7	E7-1	E7-2	E7-3	E8-1	E8-2	E8-4	E9-1	E9-2	E9-3	E9-4
Major elements (%)																	
SiO ₂	51.84	63.05	62.16	68.34	69.09	81.30	52.49	40.61	59.76	59.21	78.95	73.16	59.89	41.41	58.31	51.78	53.85
Al ₂ O ₃	22.22	11.65	14.81	7.74	2.77	3.22	9.89	10.83	3.01	16.68	1.32	9.23	14.94	11.68	12.68	12.78	16.53
Fe ₂ O ₃	9.90	13.96	8.59	13.51	21.63	9.47	21.66	32.74	28.44	11.46	12.55	10.20	8.02	30.71	16.42	22.77	8.19
MgO	0.58	0.25	0.42	0.17	0.04	0.15	0.05	0.13	0.01	0.33	0.02	0.14	0.33	0.18	0.34	0.27	0.23
CaO	0.09	0.04	0.19	0.06	0.03	0.20	0.04	0.14	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.23	0.21	0.05	0.29	0.08
Na ₂ O	1.49	0.20	0.50	0.08	0.05	0.21	0.36	0.37	0.05	0.44	0.06	0.34	0.53	0.48	0.28	0.43	0.78
K ₂ O	2.78	2.35	2.95	1.89	0.25	0.55	0.80	1.72	0.21	2.50	0.54	1.48	2.58	2.36	1.68	1.81	3.59
TiO ₂	1.47	0.35	0.47	0.54	0.70	0.46	2.06	0.75	2.47	0.98	0.63	0.47	0.78	0.66	1.77	0.76	0.74
P ₂ O ₅	0.15	0.27	0.12	0.16	0.12	0.07	0.14	0.20	0.10	0.15	0.14	0.06	0.12	0.13	0.18	0.17	0.12
MnO	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.01
LOI	9.10	7.50	9.20	6.70	3.70	3.70	10.70	12.00	4.80	7.90	4.80	4.70	12.20	11.90	7.40	8.00	15.50
S	0.42	0.75	1.11	0.61	0.31	0.32	0.97	2.06	0.24	0.61	0.72	0.28	1.42	1.89	0.20	0.52	2.83
Total	99.63	99.63	99.42	99.20	98.39	99.34	98.20	99.50	98.88	99.71	99.04	99.83	99.65	99.73	99.13	99.08	99.62
Rare earth elements (mg kg⁻¹)																	
La	29.00	34.80	37.30	22.90	47.00	24.10	26.50	38.90	15.00	26.40	30.30	16.50	37.60	33.60	28.70	30.80	42.70
Ce	57.60	68.80	72.10	45.40	92.60	47.10	48.90	74.50	27.20	55.90	55.20	31.90	77.10	66.70	54.70	62.00	89.10
Pr	7.02	7.20	7.49	4.84	10.01	5.20	6.01	8.06	3.40	6.93	5.69	3.47	8.68	7.33	6.66	7.19	10.11
Nd	27.70	25.30	25.10	16.40	35.00	18.70	22.20	28.30	11.80	27.60	21.40	12.70	32.60	26.00	25.90	27.70	37.00
Sm	5.70	4.50	4.40	3.10	6.10	3.80	4.30	4.50	1.70	5.70	3.50	2.80	5.80	4.50	4.80	5.20	7.00
Eu	1.49	0.73	0.75	0.51	1.08	0.70	0.88	0.93	0.45	1.34	0.76	0.53	1.10	0.90	1.21	1.28	1.30
Gd	5.11	5.00	4.09	2.89	6.97	4.33	3.20	3.58	1.18	5.09	3.70	3.55	4.96	3.34	4.51	4.75	4.95
Tb	1.02	1.03	0.77	0.71	1.77	0.93	0.64	0.58	0.25	0.95	0.86	0.79	0.92	0.56	0.86	0.84	0.83
Dy	5.17	6.13	5.19	4.20	11.53	6.43	3.83	3.27	1.69	5.11	6.03	4.91	5.39	3.39	4.88	5.44	4.80
Ho	1.14	1.51	1.13	1.05	2.70	1.47	0.91	0.69	0.36	1.02	1.39	1.11	1.04	0.71	1.01	1.16	0.96
Er	3.22	4.54	3.46	3.22	8.54	4.77	2.76	2.20	1.35	2.96	4.51	3.59	3.32	2.14	3.23	3.50	2.92
Tm	0.44	0.74	0.47	0.50	1.31	0.70	0.40	0.29	0.23	0.44	0.66	0.54	0.52	0.32	0.50	0.50	0.43
Yb	3.14	4.45	3.32	3.15	8.29	4.42	2.85	2.22	1.55	2.87	4.54	3.45	3.33	2.40	3.05	3.25	2.64
Lu	0.46	0.66	0.51	0.50	1.35	0.73	0.48	0.33	0.25	0.38	0.69	0.54	0.51	0.36	0.47	0.49	0.40
ΣREE	148.21	165.39	166.08	109.37	234.25	123.38	123.86	168.35	66.41	142.69	139.23	86.38	182.87	152.25	140.48	154.10	205.14
Eu/Eu*	1.25	0.70	0.80	0.77	0.75	0.78	1.08	1.05	1.44	1.13	0.96	0.76	0.93	1.05	1.18	1.17	1.00
La/Gd _{NASC}	0.92	1.13	1.48	1.29	1.10	0.90	1.35	1.77	2.07	0.84	1.33	0.76	1.23	1.63	1.03	1.05	1.40
La/Yb _{NASC}	0.89	0.76	1.09	0.70	0.55	0.53	0.90	1.70	0.94	0.89	0.65	0.46	1.09	1.36	0.91	0.92	1.57

Table 2

Samples	Modern slags			Roman slags					Smelting ashes		Roasted pyrite		Leaching tanks			
	E1-1	E1-3	E1-4	E2-2	E2-3	E2-4	E2-8	E2-9	E3-2	E3-3	E11-2	E11-3	A1-1	A1-2	A1-3	A1-4
Major elements (%)																
SiO ₂	30.87	24.67	30.30	51.58	35.00	44.60	23.59	26.58	42.02	67.76	1.36	5.39	39.28	48.65	39.62	nm
Al ₂ O ₃	1.00	2.43	1.50	13.58	3.20	4.79	5.57	7.19	8.16	12.37	0.13	0.56	11.46	12.95	1.56	15.21
Fe ₂ O ₃	63.93	56.04	58.77	17.44	58.64	47.00	68.87	63.79	16.09	6.12	92.77	84.63	19.82	14.60	52.09	11.68
MgO	0.09	0.15	0.09	0.26	0.16	0.23	0.49	0.56	0.04	0.27	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.18	0.08	0.25
CaO	5.48	2.92	4.40	0.95	0.63	0.69	1.53	1.36	0.05	0.08	0.01	0.03	0.04	0.07	3.60	0.04
Na ₂ O	0.05	0.13	0.11	0.51	0.22	0.24	0.21	0.25	0.64	2.09	0.03	0.10	0.95	1.56	0.07	0.66
K ₂ O	0.12	0.28	0.23	2.71	0.85	1.21	1.06	1.46	1.14	2.27	0.12	0.13	1.08	2.42	0.18	2.57
TiO ₂	0.10	0.13	0.12	0.55	0.58	0.65	0.28	0.29	0.52	0.87	0.01	0.03	0.47	0.76	0.37	0.49
P ₂ O ₅	0.07	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.18	0.21	0.22	0.22	0.12	0.05	0.03	0.01	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.10
MnO	0.07	0.05	0.05	0.04	0.07	0.08	0.10	0.10	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.01
LOI	0.10	11.10	2.00	11.80	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	28.20	7.70	4.80	6.70	25.70	18.30	0.10	nm
S	2.90	3.00	3.01	1.59	1.00	0.80	1.16	0.88	11.79	0.99	0.54	1.69	4.46	3.66	2.00	1.05
Total	101.88	97.96	97.64	99.51	99.63	99.80	102.02	101.90	96.99	99.59	99.28	97.60	98.93	99.59	97.81	nm
Rare earth elements (mg kg⁻¹)																
La	6.50	8.60	6.50	33.90	26.90	28.30	21.90	21.60	33.40	21.40	1.20	4.20	36.40	34.40	9.80	31.20
Ce	11.30	17.20	12.60	68.40	43.00	48.70	42.20	42.00	64.90	41.90	2.60	7.50	72.50	63.90	16.50	69.27
Pr	1.40	1.96	1.43	7.83	4.80	5.45	4.71	4.73	7.62	4.75	0.24	0.81	8.46	7.50	1.98	7.90
Nd	5.70	7.10	5.50	29.70	17.30	18.60	16.20	16.90	28.40	17.00	0.90	2.70	31.70	28.30	8.10	29.40
Sm	0.90	1.40	1.00	5.50	2.50	3.10	3.00	3.10	5.20	3.00	0.20	0.50	6.30	5.40	1.20	5.20
Eu	0.21	0.38	0.15	0.97	0.50	0.67	0.59	0.68	1.11	0.54	nd	0.12	1.34	1.00	0.29	0.80
Gd	0.89	1.18	0.78	3.96	1.92	2.59	2.78	2.41	4.12	2.05	0.22	0.58	5.49	4.79	1.00	4.50
Tb	0.13	0.20	0.14	0.78	0.39	0.52	0.54	0.44	0.66	0.39	0.05	0.13	1.09	0.82	0.16	0.60
Dy	0.82	1.17	0.82	4.62	2.39	3.17	3.23	2.46	4.16	2.56	0.21	0.68	6.26	4.88	1.07	3.80
Ho	0.19	0.29	0.20	0.95	0.50	0.77	0.70	0.59	0.87	0.57	0.05	0.17	1.23	1.02	0.25	0.70
Er	0.54	0.70	0.52	3.02	1.64	2.38	1.99	1.67	2.74	1.91	0.13	0.46	3.71	3.10	0.81	2.20
Tm	0.07	0.11	0.08	0.43	0.25	0.34	0.30	0.24	0.38	0.28	nd	0.08	0.60	0.47	0.12	0.30
Yb	0.52	0.67	0.57	2.82	1.76	2.20	1.97	1.57	2.47	2.03	0.16	0.49	3.61	3.02	0.83	2.60
Lu	0.10	0.12	0.10	0.42	0.31	0.36	0.27	0.27	0.37	0.32	0.02	0.07	0.52	0.46	0.13	0.40
ΣREE	29.27	41.08	30.39	163.30	104.16	117.15	100.38	98.66	156.40	98.70	5.98	18.49	179.21	159.06	42.24	158.87
Eu/Eu*	1.06	1.34	0.77	0.94	1.04	1.07	0.93	1.13	1.09	0.99	-	1.01	1.03	0.89	1.20	0.75
La/Gd _{NASC}	1.19	1.18	1.35	1.39	2.28	1.78	1.28	1.46	1.32	1.70	0.89	1.18	1.08	1.17	1.59	1.13
La/Yb _{NASC}	1.21	1.24	1.10	1.16	1.48	1.25	1.08	1.33	1.31	1.02	0.73	0.83	0.98	1.10	1.14	1.16

nm: not measured; nd: not detected

Table 3

Samples	Minesoils										
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10	S11
Major elements (%)											
SiO ₂	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm	nm
Al ₂ O ₃	11.85	19.06	3.19	8.24	14.57	10.01	9.52	11.41	10.69	10.88	11.11
Fe ₂ O ₃	14.03	9.78	1.32	8.28	11.90	16.40	27.92	17.24	4.07	10.69	13.38
MgO	0.43	0.50	0.12	0.22	0.46	0.51	0.36	0.43	0.25	0.85	0.85
CaO	0.07	0.06	<0.03	0.13	0.27	0.64	1.48	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.10
Na ₂ O	0.72	0.47	0.14	0.63	0.82	1.51	0.49	0.84	1.78	1.21	1.23
K ₂ O	2.78	3.31	0.98	1.61	2.61	1.64	1.66	2.11	2.11	1.78	1.84
TiO ₂	0.42	0.44	0.69	0.43	0.48	0.50	0.28	0.37	0.73	0.49	0.47
P ₂ O ₅	0.10	0.14	0.03	0.08	0.15	0.09	0.09	0.11	0.04	0.11	0.13
MnO	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.00	0.08	0.07
S	1.15	0.43	0.26	2.17	2.07	1.31	1.90	0.88	0.34	0.38	0.48
Rare earth elements (mg kg⁻¹)											
La	31.00	13.40	33.70	18.40	26.10	17.90	21.60	22.10	8.80	14.50	13.60
Ce	63.76	31.53	74.67	42.64	55.34	33.40	44.15	48.06	19.32	33.67	28.49
Pr	7.10	3.40	8.50	4.70	6.40	3.90	5.00	5.00	2.20	3.80	3.40
Nd	25.20	13.10	31.00	18.70	23.10	14.90	18.80	20.00	8.20	14.20	11.70
Sm	4.20	2.20	4.90	2.90	4.30	2.50	3.10	3.10	1.40	2.40	2.10
Eu	0.70	0.40	0.80	0.70	0.70	0.50	0.60	0.50	0.30	0.60	0.40
Gd	3.50	1.60	3.20	2.30	2.80	2.10	2.30	2.00	1.60	2.30	1.70
Tb	0.40	0.30	0.40	0.40	0.30	0.40	0.30	0.30	0.20	0.30	0.30
Dy	2.80	1.40	2.30	2.10	2.20	2.20	1.90	1.70	1.80	2.10	2.00
Ho	0.50	0.30	0.30	0.40	0.40	0.50	0.30	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40
Er	1.60	0.90	1.20	1.20	1.20	1.30	1.00	1.10	1.40	1.20	1.20
Tm	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Yb	1.80	1.10	1.30	1.40	1.50	1.40	1.30	1.40	1.60	1.40	1.50
Lu	0.30	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
ΣREE	143.06	70.03	162.67	96.24	124.74	81.40	100.75	106.06	47.62	77.27	67.19
Eu/Eu*	0.83	0.97	0.92	1.23	0.92	0.99	1.02	0.91	0.91	1.16	0.96
La/Gd _{NASC}	1.44	1.36	1.71	1.30	1.51	1.39	1.53	1.80	0.89	1.02	1.30
La/Yb _{NASC}	1.67	1.18	2.51	1.27	1.69	1.24	1.61	1.53	0.53	1.00	0.88

nm: not measured

Table 4

Samples	Extract from minesoils and gossan												Stream water (AMD)		
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10	S11	Gossan	AMD-1	AMD-2	AMD-3
pH	2.76	2.83	3.72	3.02	3.00	3.26	3.45	2.73	3.41	3.27	2.88	4.31	2.13	2.37	2.34
EC ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	1068	1326	228	895	2840	503	1850	1147	393	726	1119	115	3390	3960	2800
Ligands (ppm ^a)															
SO ₄ ²⁻	837.13	1375.28	149.49	837.13	5710.41	478.36	4305.23	1016.51	239.18	687.64	1046.41	29.90	1204.34	3394.32	1066.53
Cl ⁻	29.94	59.88	9.98	59.88	49.90	19.96	29.94	29.94	19.96	39.92	39.92	19.96	44.00	68.00	74.00
PO ₄ ³⁻	nd	0.61	0.64	0.77	0.61	0.64	nd	nd	nd	nd	nd	1.71	nd	nd	nd
Rare earth elements (ppb ^b)															
La	5.30	9.20	1.80	7.00	55.39	6.00	86.44	4.90	1.60	22.56	14.09	1.40	13.73	39.62	22.27
Ce	12.70	25.80	6.10	16.89	180.68	12.00	187.26	14.19	4.00	56.60	44.06	4.09	41.74	126.47	68.67
Pr	1.40	3.20	0.80	1.90	25.10	1.40	19.27	1.60	0.50	6.19	4.80	0.50	5.04	15.46	7.68
Nd	6.20	14.40	3.30	8.00	124.69	5.70	77.66	7.10	1.90	26.16	21.48	2.20	22.99	75.55	33.51
Sm	1.60	4.00	0.90	2.00	38.00	1.10	16.27	1.60	0.40	5.39	4.90	0.50	5.83	24.57	7.60
Eu	0.40	1.10	0.10	0.60	11.50	0.20	4.19	0.50	0.10	1.50	1.40	0.15	1.86	7.41	2.19
Gd	2.30	5.10	0.70	2.30	45.10	1.10	18.37	2.20	0.60	5.59	5.30	0.65	7.86	32.53	7.99
Tb	0.30	0.70	0.10	0.40	5.90	0.20	2.50	0.30	0.10	0.80	0.70	0.10	1.22	4.25	1.11
Dy	1.80	4.10	0.50	1.80	29.10	0.80	13.68	1.60	0.30	3.59	3.90	0.20	7.46	22.47	5.73
Ho	0.40	0.90	0.10	0.40	5.20	0.20	2.79	0.30	0.10	0.60	0.70	nd	1.57	4.00	1.07
Er	1.00	2.10	0.20	1.00	11.70	0.30	7.59	0.80	0.10	1.50	1.70	0.10	4.24	10.15	2.57
Tm	0.20	0.30	nd	0.20	1.70	0.10	1.20	0.10	nd	0.20	0.30	nd	0.68	1.46	0.39
Yb	0.90	1.70	0.30	0.80	8.30	0.20	6.49	0.70	0.10	1.00	1.30	0.10	3.67	7.60	2.13
Lu	0.10	0.30	nd	0.10	1.20	nd	1.00	0.10	nd	0.10	0.20	nd	0.53	1.06	0.29
ΣREE	34.60	72.89	14.89	43.39	543.55	29.29	444.70	35.97	9.79	131.78	104.81	9.98	118.42	372.60	163.20
Eu/Eu*	0.95	1.10	0.57	1.27	1.26	0.82	1.10	1.21	0.93	1.24	1.25	1.19	1.25	1.19	1.28
La/Gd _{NASC}	0.37	0.29	0.42	0.49	0.20	0.89	0.76	0.36	0.43	0.66	0.43	0.35	0.28	0.20	0.45
La/Yb _{NASC}	0.57	0.52	0.58	0.85	0.65	2.91	1.29	0.68	1.55	2.19	1.05	1.36	0.36	0.51	1.01

nd: not detected

^a mg L⁻¹ for AMD samples and mg kg⁻¹ for solutions extracted from minesoils.

^b μg L⁻¹ for AMD samples and μg kg⁻¹ for solutions extracted from minesoils.

Table 5

Samples	Estuary sediments		
	GE-1	GE-2	GE-3
Major elements (%)			
SiO ₂	54.24	53.24	58.26
Al ₂ O ₃	16.85	17.01	16.03
Fe ₂ O ₃	6.66	7.24	6.64
MgO	1.83	1.92	1.74
CaO	0.95	1.26	1.37
Na ₂ O	2.47	2.47	2.11
K ₂ O	2.58	2.40	2.39
TiO ₂	0.99	1.06	1.10
P ₂ O ₅	0.18	0.21	0.17
MnO	0.11	0.06	0.15
LOI	13.10	13.10	10.00
S	0.12	0.07	0.04
Total	99.96	99.97	99.96
Rare earth elements (mg kg⁻¹)			
La	43.10	42.60	45.70
Ce	84.30	82.90	91.00
Pr	10.05	9.95	10.96
Nd	36.10	37.80	41.40
Sm	7.70	7.60	8.20
Eu	1.60	1.72	1.79
Gd	6.61	6.97	7.47
Tb	1.05	1.04	1.12
Dy	6.20	6.00	6.70
Ho	1.16	1.26	1.31
Er	3.55	3.65	4.05
Tm	0.56	0.55	0.56
Yb	3.40	3.49	3.33
Lu	0.53	0.54	0.56
ΣREE	205.91	206.07	224.15
Eu/Eu*	1.02	1.07	1.04
La/Gd _{NASC}	1.06	0.99	0.99
La/Yb _{NASC}	1.23	1.18	1.33

Table 6